

Title: Annotating SDOH domains of public variables from the NaNDA database.

Summary: You are asked to fill in the domain column for each of the 223 variables in the file “NaNDA_variable_annotations_BLANK.csv”. Before annotating, you will be given the definition of each SDOH Domain 1-5, then you will be asked to assign each variable to a domain 1-5.

Procedure:

1. (Background) Your options for annotation of the domain are the numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 representing the corresponding SDOH Domains:

*Annotation Number	SDOH Domain	Description
1	Social and Community Context	The contexts in which people live, study, work, and relax.
2	Economic Stability	People's income, socioeconomic status, and cost of living, with factors such as poverty, unemployment or underemployment, food insecurity, and housing instability negatively impacting health.
3	Education Access and Quality	Early childhood education and development, graduating from high school, receiving higher education, and even English knowledge and literacy.
4	Neighborhood and Built Environment	Quality of housing, access to transportation, access to healthy foods and clean water, air quality inside and outside, and the impact of crime and violence on people who live in the area.
5	Healthcare and Quality	Access to primary care, access to specialty care, health insurance coverage, and health literacy.

2. In your .csv file, fill in the domain column with a **single** whole value 1 through 5.
 - a. To make your decision, you should use the information in columns A, B, and C, (i.e., variable name, variable label, data source).
 - b. If you do not know which domain the variable should be assigned to, or if you think it could belong to multiple domains, choose the one that most specifically describes it.
 - c. You can use each domain more than once, and you do not have to use all 5 domains.
3. (Optional) If you have notes on your annotation, you may make comments in the optional_annotation_notes column.

4. An example is included below for annotating 1 variable.

Example.

Given this variable, use the context in columns variable_name, variable_label, and data_source to choose a SDOH Domain 1-5. Record the number (1-5) of that SDOH Domain in the domain column.

<u>variable_name</u>	<u>variable_label</u>	<u>data_source</u>	<u>domain</u>	<u>optional_annotation_notes</u>
aden_emp_621320	# optometrists per sq mile w/ 2+ employees	The North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) was used to identify organizations that can be considered health care services. Establishment data was taken from the National Establishment Time Series (NETS) database. Census tracts for establishments, as well as land area per tract, were determined using the 2010 version of the US TIGER/Line shapefiles. Population figures and tract land areas were obtained from two NaNDA datasets: Neighborhood Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics of Census Tracts, United States, 2000-2010 (https://www.openicpsr.org/openicpsr/project/111107/) and Socioeconomic Status and Demographic Characteristics of Census Tracts, United States, 2008-2017 (https://www.openicpsr.org/openicpsr/project/119451/).	5	